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Centre for Development of Intellectual Property and Research

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Centre for Development of Intellectual Property and Research
Naovina Development of Intellectual Property and Research Foundation
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**THE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS OF GOODS
(REGISTRATION AND PROTECTION) ACT, 1999**
SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE AMENDMENT

SUBMITTED BY
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THE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS OF GOODS (REGISTRATION AND PROTECTION) ACT, 1999

PRELIMINARY AND DEFINITIONS (SECTION 1-5)

SECTION 1. SHORT TITLE, EXTENT AND COMMENCEMENT

Provision Overview:

1. This Act may be called the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999.
2. It extends to the whole of India.
3. It shall come into force on such date as the Central Government may, by notification, appoint.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

Registration of GI's began in the year 2004-05 after the above-mentioned law came into effect in 2003.

- **Delayed Implementation:** The provision leaves the commencement of the Act at the discretion of the Central Government. In practice, such open-ended provisions can lead to delays in enforcement, which is problematic when there is a pressing need for protection of geographical indications (GI), particularly in rapidly growing sectors like agriculture and traditional handicrafts.
- **Comparative Gap with Global Practices:** In comparison to the European Union (EU) system for geographical indications (under Regulation (EU) No. 2024/1143), there is a clearer framework for timelines regarding the protection and registration of geographical indications. In the EU, once a GI is registered, protection begins almost immediately, which reduces the risk of interim infringements.

Amendment Suggestion:

- **Defined Timelines:** Introduce a fixed timeline for the Central Government to bring the provisions of the Act into effect. For instance, a clause could be added that mandates the commencement of the Act within six months of its passage, ensuring that no undue delays prevent the application of the law.

- **Provision for Interim Protection:** As in other jurisdictions, such as the EU, interim protection should be granted to GI applicants as soon as their application is filed. This would protect producers during the often-lengthy registration process.

SECTION 2. DEFINITIONS AND INTERPRETATION

Provision Overview:

The section provides the definitions of key terms used in the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999, including “authorised user,” “geographical indication,” “deceptively similar,” and others. The section also explains how references to geographical indications should be interpreted within the context of the Act.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

1. *Lack of Clarity in Defining “Deceptively Similar” (Clause c)*

- **Lacuna:** The term “deceptively similar” is subjective, with the potential for inconsistent interpretations. The phrase “likely to deceive or cause confusion” is vague, as it does not specify whether the confusion is limited to consumers within India or extends to global consumers. Moreover, it does not consider modern challenges like e-commerce and online counterfeits, where “deceptively similar” GIs can proliferate.
- **Comparative International Issue:** In the European Union (EU), the concept of deceptiveness or confusion is more specifically defined, particularly in the context of consumer protection, and clear guidelines are issued to protect regional products against international misuse.

Amendment Suggestion: The Act should provide a more detailed definition of “*deceptively similar*” to include modern contexts, such as online marketplaces. A test could be included to determine if a geographical indication confuses consumers both locally and internationally. The amendment should also offer specific examples of what constitutes deceptive similarities, including guidelines on how to assess visual, phonetic, and conceptual similarity, as done in trademark law.

2. *Insufficient Definition of “Geographical Indication” (Clause e)*

- **Lacuna:** The definition of “geographical indication” does not fully address the complexities involved in determining the scope of protection for different types of

goods, particularly when they involve processes that occur across multiple regions or countries. Furthermore, there is no guidance on how hybrid products, which may involve components from various geographical locations, should be classified.

- **Environmental and Sustainability Issues:** The current definition does not include provisions for ensuring that products associated with a geographical indication meet environmental sustainability standards. In industries such as agriculture and handicrafts, unsustainable practices can undermine the long-term value of GIs.

Amendment Suggestion: The definition should be expanded to include a clearer process for assessing goods produced across multiple regions or countries, particularly in the context of global supply chains. There should be a provision to include environmental and sustainability criteria, requiring that GIs be granted only to goods produced using sustainable methods. This approach is already seen in other jurisdictions, such as the EU’s focus on “sustainable production practices” for GIs.

3. *Overly Broad Definition of “Goods” (Clause f)*

- **Lacuna:** The definition of “goods” is too broad, encompassing “any agricultural, natural, or manufactured goods” and “foodstuff.” While inclusivity is important, this broad categorization can lead to challenges in the classification of unique and indigenous products that do not fit neatly into these categories. This definition does not distinguish between mass-produced goods and traditional artisanal products, which may dilute the significance of GIs for small producers.
- **Comparison with International Standards:** In the EU, GIs are specifically aimed at protecting traditional, artisanal, and local products, giving special consideration to small producers. India’s broad definition risks overextending protection to goods that may not need GI status.

Amendment Suggestion: Introduce sub-categories for goods, particularly for traditional or indigenous products, to better capture the specific characteristics of Indian products, especially in agriculture and handicrafts. The amendment could include a clause that gives additional protection to artisanal goods produced by small-scale producers and indigenous communities. This would align with international best practices, where GIs prioritise traditional methods and cultural significance.

4. *Inadequate Definition of “Producer” (Clause k)*

- **Lacuna:** The definition of “producer” includes any person who produces, processes, or packages goods, including traders. This definition risks giving too much leeway to intermediaries and traders, who may not have any direct connection to the geographical origin or traditional methods of production. Traders could exploit this broad definition to register GIs without benefiting actual producers.
- **Risk of Exploitation:** By including traders or middlemen in the definition of “producer,” the law potentially allows corporations or larger businesses to dominate GI registrations, leading to an imbalance where the benefits of GIs are not fairly distributed to the actual producers, such as farmers or artisans.

Amendment Suggestion: Narrow the definition of “producer” to exclude traders and intermediaries unless they are directly involved in the production, processing, or preparation of goods in the geographical region. The amendment should also include a provision that ensures that producers—particularly small-scale and indigenous producers—have an equitable share in the registration process and its benefits. This would prevent larger corporations from monopolising GIs.

5. *Lack of Digital Provisions in the Definition of “Indication” (Clause g)*

- **Lacuna:** The definition of “indication” does not include considerations for digital representations of geographical indications, which are increasingly relevant in e-commerce and online trade. The rise of digital platforms where counterfeit products often carry deceptive geographical indications calls for a broader interpretation of the term “indication.”
- **Global Best Practice:** The EU’s GI regulations have started addressing the challenges posed by digital platforms by requiring clear labelling and protections for online sales.

Amendment Suggestion: Update the definition of “indication” to include digital and virtual representations of GIs. This would expand the scope of GI protection to e-commerce and digital platforms, ensuring that any misuse of GIs in online sales is subject to legal enforcement. Provisions should also be made to require online marketplaces to verify GI claims made by sellers.

6. *Ambiguity in the Interpretation of “Registered Proprietor” (Clause n)*

- **Lacuna:** The definition of “*registered proprietor*” allows for any association of persons, producers, or organisations to be listed as the proprietor of a GI. However, it does not specify any provisions for equitable benefit-sharing among the actual producers, particularly in cases where large organisations apply for GIs on behalf of smaller producer groups.
- **Potential Exploitation of Small Producers:** This broad definition can lead to situations where corporations or middlemen control GI registrations, leaving small-scale producers without fair representation or compensation.

Amendment Suggestion: Amend the definition to include safeguards ensuring that actual producers are represented equitably in the registration process. Introduce provisions that mandate a fair distribution of the benefits arising from the GI registration, with special consideration given to small and marginalised producers.

SECTION 3. REGISTRAR OF GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

The Controller-General of Patents, Designs, and Trade Marks shall be the Registrar of Geographical Indications, and the Central Government may appoint officers to assist the Registrar.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- **No Specific Qualifications for Officers:** The Act is silent on the qualifications or expertise required for officers appointed to assist the Registrar. This could lead to inconsistencies in the registration process and in the protection of GIs, as officers without adequate knowledge may not fully understand the complexities of geographical indications, particularly in sectors like agriculture, handicrafts, and traditional knowledge.
- **Lack of Specialization in Indian Context:** The protection of GIs in India is deeply tied to traditional knowledge and practices, especially in rural and indigenous communities. Officers dealing with GIs should have a specialised understanding of the cultural and economic significance of these indications, which the current framework does not address.

Amendment Suggestion:

- **Mandatory Expertise and Training:** Introduce a provision that outlines the minimum qualifications for officers appointed under this section, such as a background in intellectual property law, agriculture, or indigenous rights. Additionally, specialised training on GI-related issues, especially concerning Indian rural and traditional products, should be mandated.
- **Introduction of an Expert Committee:** Similar to the French system, where a National Institute of Origin and Quality (INAO) oversees GIs with a board of experts from different sectors, India could benefit from forming an expert committee within the Registrar's office to review applications and assist with complex cases.

SECTION 4. POWER OF REGISTRAR TO WITHDRAW OR TRANSFER CASES

Provision Overview:

The Registrar has the power to withdraw matters from officers and either deal with them personally or transfer them to another officer.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- **Transparency Concerns:** The provision does not mandate any transparency in the decision-making process when the Registrar withdraws or transfers cases. This could lead to arbitrary or politically influenced decisions, raising concerns about impartiality and fairness in the administration of GI registrations.
- **No External Oversight:** There is no provision for oversight or external review of the Registrar's decisions regarding case transfers, which could lead to potential abuse of power.

Amendment Suggestion:

- **Mandated Transparency and Record-Keeping:** Amend the Act to require that any decision by the Registrar to withdraw or transfer a case must be accompanied by a written, publicly accessible explanation. This explanation should outline the reasons for the decision, ensuring transparency and accountability.

- **Introduction of an Appeal Mechanism:** Introduce a provision allowing aggrieved parties to appeal decisions regarding the transfer of cases. This would ensure that any misuse of discretionary power is subject to review, similar to systems seen in jurisdictions like the United Kingdom, where judicial review can be sought in case of administrative overreach.

SECTION 5. GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS REGISTRY AND OFFICES THEREOF

Provision Overview:

1. Establishment of the Geographical Indications Registry, with its head office at a location specified by the Central Government.
2. Branch offices may also be set up for facilitating GI registrations.
3. The Central Government may define territorial limits for these offices.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- **Limited Accessibility:** The Act allows for the establishment of regional offices, but it does not specify any mechanisms to ensure that these offices are accessible, particularly to small-scale producers and artisans located in remote or rural areas. This could disproportionately impact those who are most reliant on GI protections but have the least access to legal and administrative resources.
- **Outdated Paper-Based System:** The Act presupposes a physical, office-based system for GI registrations. In the modern era, such a system can be cumbersome, particularly when digital solutions are available that would facilitate greater participation and efficiency.

Amendment Suggestion:

- **Establishing Digital Access:** Introduce provisions that mandate the establishment of an online portal for GI applications, where producers can submit their documents, track the status of their applications, and receive notifications about their cases. This would democratise access to GI protection, particularly for rural and indigenous communities who may not be able to travel to a physical office.
- **Outreach and Assistance Programs:** Mandate the creation of outreach programs to educate rural producers about the GI registration process. These programs could involve partnerships with NGOs or government bodies to ensure that even the most marginalised

groups have the opportunity to protect their goods under GI law. The EU's "CAP" initiative is an example of a similar model that India could adopt.

Comparative International Insights and Recommendations for Modernization

Global Best Practices and Comparisons:

- **European Union (EU):** The EU offers a highly structured and efficient GI registration process, including provisional protection during the application phase, well-defined timelines for processing applications, and a robust digital platform for managing GI claims. India's system, by comparison, lacks digital infrastructure, which could streamline the process significantly.
- **France:** France's National Institute of Origin and Quality (INAO) is a model for a centralised, expert-driven body overseeing GIs. It incorporates scientific and cultural expertise into the registration process, which is critical in evaluating the authenticity and uniqueness of GIs, particularly in the food and wine sectors.

Recommendations for India:

1. **Expand the Online GI Portal:** Introduce a fully digital platform similar to the EU's E-BACCHUS system, which allows users to register, search, and track GIs online. The portal should also offer guides in local languages, making it accessible to non-English speakers.
2. **Mandatory Certification of Officers and Experts:** Officers handling GI registrations must undergo training in intellectual property law and the cultural significance of GIs. Introducing an expert review board, as seen in France, would further enhance the rigour of the process.
3. **Strengthening Enforcement in Digital Markets:** India should include provisions to monitor the misuse of GIs on digital platforms like Amazon and Flipkart. This could be supported by collaboration with e-commerce platforms, requiring sellers to provide GI certification when listing goods as having geographical indications.

REGISTRATION PROCESS & APPLICATION (SECTIONS 6-20)

SECTION 6. THE REGISTER AND CLASSIFICATION OF GOODS

Provision Overview:

The Act establishes a register called the *Geographical Indications Register*, which consists of two parts:

Part A - For registered geographical indications (GIs) of goods.

Part B - For authorised users of registered geographical indications.

The Act mandates that goods be classified in accordance with the international classification of goods for the purposes of registration.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The current classification system relies on an international classification, which may not fully accommodate the diversity and specificity of India's unique traditional products, especially agricultural and handicraft items that do not always fit into predefined categories.
- The register in its current form may not be user friendly or easily accessible to the general public, particularly small-scale producers and indigenous communities.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Introduce sub-categories or expanded classifications specific to Indian traditional and indigenous goods. This could include separate classifications for regional handicrafts, cultural products, and traditional farming techniques, ensuring that unique Indian goods are accurately reflected.
- Modernise the GI Register by introducing a more accessible, publicly available, and searchable online database. This should include simple language guides for producers, small businesses, and indigenous communities to understand the registration process and *how their goods are classified*.

SECTION 7. PROHIBITION OF REGISTRATION OF CERTAIN GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 7 lists categories of GIs that cannot be registered, including:

1. GIs that are likely to deceive or cause confusion.
2. GIs that are contrary to law or morality.
3. GIs that are generic or have become common names for goods.

4. GIs that conflict with the name of plant varieties or animal breeds, or which falsely suggest a connection with living persons or organisations.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The term “generic” is not well-defined, leaving ambiguity over when a GI is considered generic. This could result in unfair denial of GIs for products that may be widely known but still have unique regional characteristics.
- The provision does not adequately address the rise of counterfeit goods or false geographical indications, particularly in digital marketplaces.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Provide a clearer definition of “generic” goods. This could include guidelines outlining how long a term must be in use, the scope of its usage, and any specific regional characteristics that can qualify a product for GI protection despite its popularity.
- Strengthen the prohibition by including explicit language about the misuse of GIs in online markets. This should be paired with enforcement mechanisms for tracking and penalising the digital sale of counterfeit goods claiming GI status.

SECTION 8. PERSONS WHO CAN APPLY FOR REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

Under Section 8, any “*association of persons*” or “*producers*” or any organisation or authority established by law, representing the interests of the producers of the concerned goods, can apply for the registration of a geographical indication.

The section also permits government authorities to apply for GIs to protect national interests.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The term “*association of persons*” is vague and may exclude smaller producer groups or indigenous communities that are not formally organised but still have legitimate claims to a GI.
- The section does not address the issue of intermediary control, where middlemen or corporations apply for GIs on behalf of smaller producer groups, potentially leading to exploitation or unequal benefit-sharing.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Expand the definition to include informal producer groups, cooperatives, and traditional indigenous communities, even if they are not formally registered as associations. This would give them the same standing as formal entities when applying for GIs.
- Include a provision that mandates equitable representation of the actual producers in the GI application process, with safeguards ensuring that intermediaries do not monopolise control or profit disproportionately.

SECTION 9. CONDITIONS FOR REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

Section 9 outlines specific conditions for registering a geographical indication, including:

1. That the GI must not be misleading or deceptive.
2. That it must not offend public order or morality.
3. That the GI should not be generic or already well-known.
4. That it must not cause confusion with an existing trademark.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The conditions for avoiding confusion with an existing trademark are not clearly defined, which could create conflicts between GI holders and trademark owners.
- No provision is made for environmental sustainability, meaning that goods registered under a GI might not necessarily adhere to sustainable or ethical production methods.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Provide clearer guidelines or dispute resolution mechanisms specifically for conflicts between geographical indications and trademarks, ensuring that the rights of both GI holders and trademark owners are respected without arbitrary decisions.
- Introduce a requirement that goods applying for GI registration must meet basic environmental and ethical standards, particularly in industries like agriculture and handicrafts where production can impact local ecosystems.

SECTION 10. APPLICATION FOR REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

The process for applying for a GI involves submitting a detailed application to the Registrar, including particulars such as the description of the goods, the geographical area, proof of the

goods' uniqueness and the method of production. The Registrar can accept or reject the application or ask for additional information.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The application process can be complex and bureaucratic, creating barriers for small-scale producers and traditional artisans who may not have the resources or expertise to navigate the system.
- There is no mention of technological innovations that could ease the application process, such as digital submissions or e-verification systems.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Simplify the application process by introducing a tiered system for smaller producers or groups with limited resources. This could include a fast-track application process with reduced fees or assistance from a government body to help complete the application.
- Allow for online submissions and tracking of applications through a dedicated portal. This will streamline the process, particularly for rural applicants who may find it challenging to submit physical documents.

SECTION 11. EXAMINATION OF APPLICATION

Provision Overview:

The Registrar examines every application to ensure that it complies with the Act and has the power to either accept, reject, or request modifications to the application. If the application is accepted, it is advertised in the GI Journal for potential opposition.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The examination process may take a considerable amount of time, particularly for applications from under-resourced applicants who cannot afford to respond to repeated queries or objections.
- There is no mention of collaboration with scientific or technical experts who might better assess whether a product qualifies for GI protection based on its unique qualities.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Set a time limit for the examination process to ensure that applicants receive timely responses. Additionally, provide government-supported legal assistance for small

producers and indigenous communities to help them address the Registrar's concerns or objections.

- Establish a panel of experts from various industries, including agriculture, handicrafts, and environmental sciences, to assist the Registrar in examining applications. This would ensure that decisions are well-informed and based on a deeper understanding of the goods.

SECTION 12. REGISTRATION OF HOMONYMOUS GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 12 allows for the registration of homonymous GIs, i.e., geographical indications that are identical or similar in name but pertain to goods from different regions. The Registrar must ensure that consumers are not confused and that both GIs are clearly distinguished from each other.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- Homonymous GIs can still cause confusion, particularly in international markets where consumers may not be familiar with the distinctions between similar names from different regions.
- There is no clear guidance on how to handle disputes between two regions that claim similar names, leading to potential legal conflicts.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Mandate the use of additional qualifying terms or labels for homonymous GIs, such as specifying the country or region prominently on the label. This would reduce the risk of confusion, particularly in global trade.
- Introduce a mediation or arbitration mechanism for resolving disputes between regions or countries claiming homonymous GIs. This could prevent lengthy court battles and foster cooperation between competing regions.

SECTION 13. PROHIBITION OF REGISTRATION OF NAMES OF GOODS AS GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 13 prohibits the registration of a product name as a geographical indication if it has become a generic name or if it misleads consumers about the true origin of the goods.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The determination of whether a name has become generic can be subjective, with no clear guidelines for the criteria used.
- There is no provision for re-registering a product name if it becomes de-genericized, i.e., if the public once again associates the product with a specific region.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Clarify the criteria for determining genericness by outlining specific factors such as the period of use, geographic distribution, and consumer perception. This would reduce the subjectivity and improve the fairness of decisions.
- Introduce a mechanism that allows for the re-registration of names that were once considered generic but have regained their association with a specific region due to effective marketing, quality control, or public awareness campaigns.

SECTION 14. OPPOSITION TO REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

Any person may oppose a registration within three months of its advertisement or readvertisement of an application for registration or within such further period, not exceeding one month, in the aggregate. The Registrar informs the applicant, who must respond with a counter-statement within two months. If not, the application is deemed abandoned. Both parties may submit evidence and request a hearing. The Registrar then decides whether to grant registration. If the parties are non-residents, they may need to provide security for costs. Corrections to notices or counter-statements may be allowed.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The timeframe for opposition (three months, plus one month extension) may not be sufficient for parties with legitimate interests, especially those based abroad, to prepare their cases. With the rise of international trade and global markets, foreign entities may require more time.

- The provision for security costs for non-resident applicants or opponents may discourage foreign parties from engaging in the process, even if they have a legitimate claim.
- Lack of provision for online dispute resolution mechanisms. In today's digital age, geographical limitations should not prevent timely submission of opposition or evidence.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Extend the opposition period to four months or allow more flexibility for further extensions, particularly for foreign parties, to ensure fair participation.
- Introduce guidelines for assessing security deposits based on the specific circumstances of each case, reducing arbitrary or unnecessarily high requirements for foreign entities.
- Introduce mandatory online submission portals for opposition and counter-statements and allow for virtual hearings to streamline the process.

SECTION 15. CORRECTION AND AMENDMENT

Provision Overview:

The Registrar may permit to correct errors or amend applications at any time, whether before or after acceptance of an application for registration under section 11 (Application for Registration). If the amendment involves dividing an application into multiple ones, the initial filing date applies to the divided applications.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The power to amend applications or correct errors is left entirely at the discretion of the Registrar, with no clear criteria for when such amendments are allowed. This could lead to inconsistent decision-making or abuse of discretion.
- The provision does not account for technological errors, such as those that might occur in an online filing system.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Establish clearer criteria or guidelines outlining the circumstances under which amendments or corrections are allowed. This will promote transparency and reduce arbitrary decisions.
- Include provisions to address errors arising from digital platforms (e.g., system malfunctions) and allow for corrections without penalty if due to technical issues.

SECTION 16. REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

If a geographical indication application is accepted and unopposed, or opposition is decided in favour of the applicant, the Registrar registers the geographical indication.

The registration date is the date of the original application. Certificates of registration are issued, and clerical errors can be corrected.

If the registration of a geographical indication is not completed within twelve months from the date of the application due to the applicant's default, the Registrar may, after providing notice to the applicant in the prescribed manner, consider the application abandoned unless it is completed within the time specified in the notice.

The Registrar also has the authority to amend the register or a registration certificate to correct any clerical errors or obvious mistakes.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section focuses on physical certification and issuance. With the increase in digital documentation, physical copies might not always be the most efficient or environmentally friendly approach.
- There is no provision for post-registration monitoring of geographical indications, particularly in light of evolving markets and the rise of counterfeit goods, especially online.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Allow for electronic certification and registration processes. Certificates could be issued digitally unless physical copies are expressly requested.
- Introduce a requirement for periodic checks to ensure the registered geographical indication continues to be valid and is not being misused in e-commerce platforms.

SECTION 17. APPLICATION FOR REGISTRATION AS AUTHORISED USER

Provision Overview:

Producers of goods can apply to be registered as authorised users of a geographical indication. They must provide supporting documents. The same provisions for:

- a) the filing and examination of the application;

- b) the refusal and acceptance of registration;
- c) withdrawal of acceptance of application;
- d) advertisement of application;
- e) opposition to registration;
- f) correction or error in an amendment of the application; and
- g) registration

shall apply to authorised users as for geographical indications.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The current provision may not adequately address the global supply chain and manufacturing processes. A producer in one country may use ingredients from multiple sources, raising questions about whether they are truly entitled to be registered as an authorised user.
- The provision doesn't account for digital marketplace proliferation. Unauthorised users may claim geographical indication status on platforms like Amazon or eBay.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Clarify the definition of a “producer” in light of complex, global supply chains. Introduce a certification mechanism for verifying the origin of components in products to ensure accurate claims of geographical indication use.
- Require authorised users to display proof of registration on online platforms and strengthen enforcement measures for misuse of geographical indications in digital markets.

SECTION 18. DURATION, RENEWAL, REMOVAL AND RESTORATION OF REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

Geographical indication registrations are valid for ten years and can be renewed. authorised user registrations are also for ten years or until the geographical indication registration expires. To renew the registration, the proprietor or authorised user must apply and pay the prescribed fee within the specified period. The Registrar will send a notice before the registration expires, outlining the conditions for renewal. If the renewal process is not completed in time, the Registrar may remove the geographical indication or authorised user

from the register. However, if the required fee and surcharge are paid within six months after the expiration, the registration can still be renewed for another ten years. If a geographical indication or authorised user is removed due to non-payment, the Registrar may restore it within one year of the expiration, provided the fee is paid, and renew the registration for another ten years.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The ten-year duration for geographical indication registration and renewal may not reflect the rapid pace of market changes. A product or indication may become obsolete or irrelevant in a shorter time frame due to shifts in production techniques, consumer preferences, or environmental conditions.
- The notice process relies on physical communication, which could be outdated and cause unnecessary delays.
- The current framework may not adequately account for the impact of climate change on geographical indications. If a region becomes unable to produce the goods associated with a registered geographical indication due to climate effects, there is no clear mechanism to address this.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Introduce a provision for intermediate reviews at five-year intervals, where the Registrar can evaluate whether the geographical indication still meets the criteria for registration and remains in active use.
- Modernise the notification system to ensure that renewal notices are sent electronically via email and other secure communication platforms to ensure timeliness.
- Include provisions for reassessing or revoking geographical indication registrations if climate change or environmental degradation prevents the continued production of the indicated goods.

SECTION 19. EFFECT OF REMOVAL FROM REGISTER FOR FAILURE TO PAY FEE FOR RENEWAL

Provision Overview:

Even if a geographical indication is removed for non-payment of renewal fees, it remains protected for one year, preventing others from registering the same indication unless certain conditions are met.

- (a) that there has been no bona fide trade use of the geographical indication which has been removed within the two years immediately preceding its removal; or
- (b) that no deception or confusion would be likely to arise from the use of the geographical indication which is the subject of the application for registration by reason of any previous use of the geographical indication which has been removed.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The one-year grace period for maintaining rights after removal from the register is relatively short, especially for small producers or indigenous communities that may need more time to re-establish compliance.
- The provision only covers trade use within the two years prior to removal. It doesn't account for situations where production or sales may have been paused temporarily due to external factors like pandemics, natural disasters, or geopolitical issues.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Extend the grace period to two years, especially for smaller producers, to allow them more time to rectify issues related to non-payment of fees or other administrative lapses.
- Allow for exemptions in cases where external factors beyond the applicant's control have impacted the bona fide use of the geographical indication.

SECTION 20. NO ACTION FOR INFRINGEMENT OF UNREGISTERED GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION

Provision Overview:

No legal action to prevent, or to recover damages for, the infringement of an unregistered geographical indication can be taken for unregistered geographical indications. However, passing off actions (misrepresentation of goods) remain unaffected.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The prohibition on legal action for unregistered geographical indications may unfairly disadvantage traditional or indigenous communities that lack the resources to register their geographical indications.
- The provision does not reflect the complexities of digital infringement, where goods can be sold globally and enforcement can be challenging.

Amendment Suggestion:

- Introduce an exception for indigenous or traditional communities, allowing them to bring passing-off actions for unregistered geographical indications that they have used for a significant period.
- Include specific provisions to address online infringements of both registered and unregistered geographical indications, with more robust mechanisms for tracking and penalising digital infringers.

OPPOSITION, CORRECTION AND RECTIFICATION

(SECTIONS 21 – 30)

SECTION 21. RIGHTS CONFERRED BY REGISTRATION

Provision Overview:

Section 21 of the GI Act, 1999 states the rights that are conferred on a person upon registration.

It provides for the following:

- The right to both the registered proprietor and the authorised users to seek relief for infringement of the GI as provided under the act. [21(1)(a)]
- The exclusive right to the authorised users to use the GI in relation to the registered goods. [21(1)(b)]
- The right to exclusive use may be subject to any conditions or limitations imposed at the time of registration. [21(2)]
- Where there are multiple authorised users of the same or similar GIs, these users do not gain rights over each other merely by registration but hold the same rights as they would against others if they were the sole authorised user. [21(3)]

Legal Lacunas Identified:

Section 21(1)(a) provides the right to both registered proprietors as well as authorised users to bring action against infringement. However, the use of the word “and” creates ambiguity as to whether the registered proprietor, in every case, needs to implead the authorised users for an action of infringement to be valid, or a standalone action by the registered proprietor alone is enough. This question was addressed by the Madhya Pradesh High Court in *Scotch Whisky Association v. J.K. Enterprises, 2023 SCC OnLine MP 5352* recently where the court clarified that registered proprietors need not implement an authorised user to file a suit of infringement; a standalone action by the registered proprietor is valid.

Amendment Suggestion:

With respect to section 21(1)(a), while the position has been clarified by the MP High Court recently, the same does not have a binding value on all courts. If the question is raised in other High Courts or even the Supreme Court, there is scope of confusion and improper interpretation. Hence, it is recommended that the position should be clarified by the legislature in the form of explanation to the provision.

SECTION 22. INFRINGEMENT OR REGISTERED GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 22 of the GI Act, 1999 talks about the infringement of registered GIs. Section 22(1) outlines the conditions under which a registered GI is considered infringed. It provides three broad categories:

- Use of a GI in a manner that misleads people as to the true geographical origin of goods.
- Unfair competition, including passing off.
- Using another GI in a misleading manner, even if the statement is literally true.

The explanations provide further clarification on acts that are considered unfair competition, including creating confusion, false allegations, and misleading representations. Section 22(2) empowers the Central Government to provide additional protection to certain goods or classes of goods by issuing a notification to that effect in the official gazette. This is in line with Article 23.1 of the TRIPS agreement, which obliges India to prohibit the use of geographical indication which identifies wines or spirits not originating in the place indicated by the GI. The only difference is that the Government’s power under the subsection goes

beyond wines and spirits. Section 22(3) states that if any person who is not an authorised user of the GI registered in respect of the goods notified under Section 22(2), uses any other GI to such goods not originating in the place indicated by such other GI by expression such as “kind”, “style”, “imitation” or the like expression shall infringe the registered GI. Section 22(4) talks about the exhaustion of remedy in case of lawfully acquired goods. However, it states that a good, lawfully purchased, cannot further be sold if its condition has been “impaired” after being put in the market. The last part is about the protection of the rights of proprietors and authorised users, so that their goodwill is not hampered.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

Under Section 22(4) the term “impaired condition” can be broadly construed to mean anything. The intention of the legislature to safeguard the right of authorised users is laudable but the statutory text may lead to confusion. The clarification has been provided by Mr. Stephen Ladas, when he talks about trademarks: *“The proper reconciliation of the scheme of interests involved is to allow these articles to be sold under the original mark provided they are not offered for sale in such a manner that prospective purchasers are likely to regard the goods as being the goods in their original form. Thus the purchaser must be put on notice that the article is a repaired or reconditioned one and not the original article of the proprietor of the trademark.On the other hand, if the repair or reconditioning involves the introduction of important components not of the proprietor's manufacture, so that there is in effect an alteration of the genuine goods of the proprietor, the use on such goods of the trademark of the proprietor is not a fair use of such mark, since such an activity may both injure the goodwill of the proprietor and may deceive the public. A bare statement or representation that the article is repaired or reconditioned will not suffice in such cases to avoid injury to the proprietor's goodwill or deception of the public.”* [Kailasam: Law of Trademarks & Geographical Indications K C Kailasam & Ramu Vedaraman]

Amendment Suggestion:

It is recommended that section 22(4), especially the part *“except where the condition of goods is impaired after they have been put in the market”* be amended and further clarified so as to specify the extent of impairment that may cause infringement and warrant action by the registered proprietor, and authorised users.

SECTION 25. PROHIBITION OF REGISTRATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION AS TRADE MARK

Provision Overview:

Section 25 is in line with Article 22.3 of TRIPS which requires the national legislation to allow at the request of an interested party to “refuse or invalidate the registration of the trade mark which contains or consists of a geographical indication with respect to goods not originating in the territory indicated, if use of the indication in the trade mark for such goods in that country is of such a nature as to mislead the public as to the true place of origin.”

It provides the registrar under the Trade Marks Act of 1999, the power to either take suo moto cognizance, or on request of “interested parties” to refuse the registration of trade mark or invalidate the registration of the trade mark, if —

- “(a) it contains or consists of a geographical indication with respect to the goods or class or classes of goods not originating in the territory of a country, or a region or locality in that territory which such geographical indication indicates, if use of such geographical indications in the trade mark for such goods, is of such a nature as to confuse or mislead the persons as to the true place of origin of such goods or class or classes of goods;*
- (b) contains or consists of a geographical indication identifying goods or class or classes of goods notified under section 22(2).”*

Legal Lacunas Identified:

Under section 25, the power has been provided to the registrar under the Trade Marks Act of 1999, to either take suo-moto action or act on request of interested parties and refuse/invalidate misleading trademarks, which are for goods, not originating in a particular territory. Given the intent of the section, which is not merely to safeguard the registered proprietor, but to also ensure that consumers are not misled, only vesting the right with “interested parties” to request refusal/invalidation limits the remedy.

Amendment Suggestion:

Section 25 may be amended and the right to request refusal/invalidation if misleading trade marks should not be merely limited to interested parties.

ENFORCEMENT AND INFRINGEMENT (SECTIONS 31-35)

SECTION 31. APPEALS TO THE HIGH COURT

Provision Overview:

Section 31 allows an aggrieved person to appeal against an order or decision of the Registrar concerning a GI registration. This appeal must be filed with the High Court within three months from the date of the order. However, the Act allows for a delay in filing the appeal if the appellant can show “sufficient cause” for the delay. This provision is crucial for ensuring judicial oversight of the Registrar's decisions.

In the European Union (EU), the appeals process is similarly structured, but appeals must be made to a judicial authority within two months, providing a shorter window for challenging decisions. This aligns with their focus on timely dispute resolution. The Australian Geographical Indications Committee allows for appeals within 60 days, emphasizing expedience.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The Act does not clarify what constitutes "sufficient cause" for condonation of delay, which may result in inconsistencies in its application. But if they specify it will be limited, so it should be left to judges discretion, and not make it rigid like in case of A&C act.

Amendment Suggestion:

Introduction of parameters to determine what qualifies as "sufficient cause" for delay, such as illness or unavoidable procedural delays. This would bring consistency and transparency in handling delayed appeals.

SECTION 34. PROCEDURE FOR APPLICATION FOR RECTIFICATION, ETC., BEFORE HIGH COURT

Provision Overview:

This section provides the procedure for rectifying the GI register in case of errors or wrongful entries. Applications for rectification can be filed directly before the High Court. This ensures that any errors, whether by mistake or malfeasance, can be corrected by judicial intervention, safeguarding the integrity of the GI register.

In New Zealand, a similar process exists but with a simpler route. Administrative errors can be corrected without requiring a court's intervention, thus making the process quicker and less cumbersome. Appeals to higher courts are only necessary in complex or contentious

cases. The EU also offers an online rectification system for minor corrections, which avoids overburdening courts.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The lack of a specific timeline for the Registrar to implement rectifications. This can lead to delays in enforcing the rectification orders issued by the High Court.

Amendment Suggestion:

Set a clear deadline for the Registrar to implement the rectification, as followed in South Korea. This would ensure that the rectification process is completed in a timely manner and also introduce an online platform for submitting and processing minor rectification requests, like in the EU, making the process faster and more accessible for all stakeholders.

SECTION 35. APPEARANCE OF REGISTRAR IN LEGAL PROCEEDINGS

Provision Overview:

This section empowers the Registrar to appear in any legal proceedings related to geographical indications. The Registrar can also file written statements in lieu of appearing in person. The purpose is to ensure that the Registrar plays an active role in upholding the integrity of the GI system during legal disputes.

In Australia, the Registrar's participation in legal proceedings is restricted to cases of public interest or where the Registrar's intervention is deemed necessary. Similarly, the EUIPO (European Union Intellectual Property Office) intervenes in cases only when critical public interest is involved, thereby streamlining the Registrar's role to more impactful cases.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The Indian GI Act gives the Registrar wide discretion to choose whether to participate in legal proceedings. This could result in the Registrar not being involved in critical cases, where their input may be essential for preserving the GI regime's integrity.

His presence may lead to conflict of interest, as their office itself mandates it, the public interest has to be defined.

Amendment Suggestion:

The Registrar's appearance should be mandated in cases involving significant public interest or economic impact, following the Australian model. This would ensure that the Registrar's expertise is available in critical disputes.

SECTION 37. MEANING OF APPLYING GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

This section outlines what constitutes the application of a geographical indication (GI) on goods. It covers a wide range of uses, from placing a GI on goods or packaging to using it in advertisements or business documentation.

In the EU, the definition of applying GIs is more granular, differentiating between direct application (e.g., labeling products) and indirect application (e.g., promotional material). Japan adopts a similar approach, ensuring that only authorised users of GIs can use them in product branding and marketing.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The broad definition in the Indian Act could unintentionally penalize entities that may reference a GI incidentally in advertisements or other commercial contexts without fraudulent intent. How would it address this in the digital world?

Amendment Suggestion:

The definition of "application" should be refined to focus on commercial use intended to mislead or misrepresent the origin of the goods. The EU's approach of excluding incidental references could be a useful model.

SECTION 38. FALSIFYING AND FALSELY APPLYING GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 38 criminalises the falsification or unauthorised use of a geographical indication. The burden of proving that the use of a GI was authorised lies with the accused. This section plays a crucial role in protecting the value and authenticity of GIs in India.

In the EU, falsification of GIs is considered a form of counterfeiting, with both criminal and civil penalties. In China, penalties for false GI application are strictly enforced, but the laws also provide clearer guidelines on how authorization is verified.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The burden of proof on the accused in India is relatively heavy, and the Act does not clearly outline what constitutes valid evidence of authorization. This could lead to ambiguity and difficulties in enforcement and no definition of authorised user and deceptively similar is provided under this section.

Amendment Suggestion:

Consider easing the burden of proof for smaller businesses or individual sellers by shifting the emphasis to demonstrating "intent" for commercial-scale falsification and specify who the authorised person is.

SECTION 39. PENALTY FOR APPLYING FALSE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

Provision Overview:

Section 39 prescribes a minimum penalty of six months of imprisonment and a fine for anyone who falsely applies a geographical indication. This section acts as a deterrent for GI infringement, ensuring that the commercial use of GIs is protected.

In the EU, penalties for the misuse of GIs can range from fines to criminal charges, depending on the severity of the offense. South Korea imposes stricter penalties, including the confiscation of goods and fines for GI violations.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The section allows for reduced punishment if the court finds "adequate and special reasons," but it does not define what these reasons are. This opens the door to inconsistent application of the law.

Amendment Suggestion:

Specify what constitutes "adequate and special reasons" for leniency, such as unintentional violations or first-time offenses. Japan's GI Act provides clear examples of cases where penalties can be reduced.

SECTION 40. PENALTY FOR SELLING GOODS TO WHICH FALSE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION IS APPLIED

Provision Overview:

This section imposes penalties on sellers who sell goods bearing false geographical indications, but it offers a defence if the seller can prove that they acted innocently or took reasonable precautions to avoid the infringement.

In the EU, sellers can defend themselves by showing that they conducted due diligence in verifying the authenticity of the goods. Australia has similar provisions, allowing sellers to avoid liability if they can demonstrate that they took reasonable steps to ensure compliance.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The burden of proof for sellers in India is relatively high, as they must demonstrate innocence or that they took reasonable precautions, which could be particularly difficult for small traders with limited resources. Ambiguity in “Reasonable Precautions”.

Amendment Suggestion:

Implement a “due diligence” standard where sellers need only demonstrate reasonable efforts to verify the authenticity of goods, similar to the EU model.

SECTION 41. ENHANCED PENALTY ON SECOND OR SUBSEQUENT CONVICTION

Provision Overview:

Section 41 provides for enhanced penalties, including higher fines and longer imprisonment terms, for individuals who are convicted of GI violations more than once. This section serves as a deterrent for repeat offenders.

In China, repeat offenders face severe penalties, including confiscation of property and revocation of business licences. The EU imposes stricter fines and may ban businesses from further GI-related activities for repeat violations.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

While the section enhances penalties, it does not outline any mechanisms for monitoring or identifying repeat offenders, which may limit its effectiveness in practice.

Amendment Suggestion:

Establish a national database to track individuals and businesses convicted of GI offences, similar to China's registry, to ensure that repeat offenders are easily identified.

SECTION 42. PENALTY FOR FALSELY REPRESENTING A GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION AS REGISTERED

Provision Overview:

Section 42 specifies that a court will not take cognizance of any offence under the GI Act unless a complaint is made by the Registrar or a person aggrieved by the unauthorised use of a geographical indication. It essentially ensures that cases of GI infringement are only prosecuted when reported by an interested party.

In the European Union (EU), both public authorities and individual producers or groups can file complaints about unauthorised GI use. Similarly, Australia allows recognized producers or associations to raise complaints, with their IP office playing an active role in prosecuting violations. In China, the authorities often take proactive action, especially when the infringement affects public interest.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The Registrar's role is limited to initiating complaints. The Act doesn't provide for proactive enforcement measures, leaving the onus on aggrieved parties or registered producers. This may result in smaller producers, who may lack resources, not pursuing action. There could be compilation when dealing with conflicting GI under Section 42(3)(c).

Amendment Suggestion:

India could introduce provisions allowing the Registrar or other government bodies to take suo moto cognizance of GI violations, following the example of China, where government bodies often play a larger role in protecting GIs.

SECTION 43. PENALTY FOR IMPROPERLY DESCRIBING A PLACE OF BUSINESS AS CONNECTED WITH THE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS REGISTRY

Provision Overview:

Section 43 lays down the liabilities for offences committed by companies under the Act. If a company is found to be guilty of GI infringement, any person in charge of the company at the

time of the offence can be held liable. This provision is meant to ensure accountability within corporate entities, preventing companies from hiding behind their corporate structure to avoid responsibility. This section also provides that if the person in charge can prove that the offence was committed without their knowledge, or that they had exercised due diligence to prevent the commission of the offence, they may not be held personally liable.

In Australia, similar provisions exist under their intellectual property laws, holding corporate directors and officers accountable for infringement unless they can prove due diligence. New Zealand applies similar corporate liability for GI violations, but also emphasises the importance of robust internal compliance mechanisms to prevent violations.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

While the Indian GI Act provides personal liability for company officials, it doesn't clearly outline what constitutes "due diligence" or how companies can establish effective compliance systems to avoid liability. This could lead to inconsistent application of the law.

Amendment Suggestion:

Provide detailed guidelines on what constitutes "due diligence" and how companies can set up compliance systems to avoid infringement. New Zealand's approach of requiring corporate compliance policies for intellectual property could be adopted.

SECTION 44. PENALTY FOR FALSIFICATION OF ENTRIES IN THE REGISTER

Provision Overview:

Section 44 relates to the evidence required for proving the origin of goods imported by sea, which may be necessary in cases of GI infringement. It ensures that in the case of an offence related to a geographical indication, proper documentation of the goods' origin must be presented. This section helps in verifying whether the goods bearing a geographical indication truly originate from the region they claim to.

In the European Union, customs authorities play a crucial role in intercepting goods suspected of infringing GIs, with a robust system for verifying the origin of imported goods. China has also established strong customs enforcement mechanisms to check for GI violations, with strict penalties for falsely declaring the origin of goods.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The Indian Act lacks specific enforcement measures for customs authorities to verify and act against suspected GI infringements at the border. There are no clear procedures for how customs officials should handle suspected GI violations, leading to potential gaps in enforcement.

Amendment Suggestion:

Introduction of detailed procedures for customs authorities to follow when handling imported goods suspected of GI violations, as implemented in the EU. This could include random checks and the ability to seize suspected infringing goods.

SECTION 45. NO OFFENCE IN CERTAIN CASES

Provision Overview:

This section outlines situations where actions that might otherwise constitute a GI violation are permitted under the GI Act or other laws, such as the use of generic terms or traditional methods of describing goods.

The EU ensures that generic terms (like "cheddar" for cheese) are not protected as GIs, balancing the protection of authentic GIs with broader consumer rights. New Zealand similarly recognizes the difference between generic and specific terms, allowing for a more flexible interpretation of GI use.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

The section does not clearly define what constitutes “generic use” which could lead to misuse of this exception and potential conflicts with registered GIs.

Amendment Suggestion:

Provide a detailed list of generic terms that are excluded from GI protection, following the EU model. This would reduce ambiguity and prevent unnecessary legal disputes.

MISCELLANEOUS AND TRANSITIONAL PROVISIONS

(SECTIONS 46-60)

SECTION 46. FORFEITURE OF GOODS

Provision Overview:

This section empowers the court to order the forfeiture of goods related to offences under the act. It ensures that offenders do not profit from illegal activities involving false geographical indications (GI). The provision also covers appeals against forfeiture orders. This is a deterrent measure, ensuring that not only are offenders punished, but the goods involved are also confiscated, preventing their circulation in the market.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- While the section allows forfeiture of goods involved in an offence, it lacks clarity on the procedure for identifying, handling, and disposing of such goods. There is also no detailed provision for protecting the rights of third parties who may have a legitimate claim over the goods.
- Determining the specific goods to be forfeited might be complex, especially when they are part of a larger batch or have already entered the market.

Amendment Suggestion:

Introduce clear guidelines on the procedure for identifying, handling, and disposing of forfeited goods. The act should include provisions for protecting the rights of innocent third parties who may have legitimate claims on forfeited goods (e.g., retailers unaware of the counterfeit nature). To ensure transparency and prevent misuse, especially in cases where the goods have changed hands without knowledge of their illegal status.\

SECTION 47. EXEMPTION FOR CERTAIN PERSONS IN ORDINARY COURSE OF BUSINESS

Provision Overview:

This provides immunity to individuals working in the production process, such as manufacturers or printers, if they can prove that they were unaware of the falsification of geographical indications. This Protects innocent employees or intermediaries who were not aware of the GI misuse, balancing enforcement with fairness.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section relies heavily on the accused proving innocence by showing they took “reasonable precautions.” However, what constitutes “reasonable precautions” is not clearly defined. This lack of specificity could lead to inconsistent interpretations.
- The burden of proof rests on the accused to demonstrate they acted in good faith, which could lead to disputes over what actions count as reasonable. This can cause prolonged litigation.

Amendment Suggestion:

Define what constitutes “reasonable precautions” for persons engaged in ordinary business activities. The act should provide an exhaustive list of actions considered as reasonable precautions (e.g., verifying suppliers, maintaining records of purchases). Clear guidelines would reduce ambiguity and help courts decide such cases more consistently.

SECTION 48. PROCEDURE WHERE INVALIDITY OF REGISTRATION IS PLEADED

Provision Overview:

Allows a defendant to challenge the validity of the geographical indication registration. The court can adjourn proceedings to allow time for rectification applications to be filed in the High Court. This section offers a defense mechanism for individuals accused of offences, ensuring due process by allowing them to challenge the legitimacy of the GI in question.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section lacks clear guidelines on what constitutes a “prima facie tenable” defense when the accused pleads invalidity of the geographical indication’s registration. There is also no mention of what happens if rectification proceedings are unduly delayed.
- Courts could struggle with balancing the need for swift justice with the time it takes to determine GI validity in a separate rectification process, potentially leading to indefinite adjournments of cases.

Amendment Suggestion:

Include a defined timeline within which rectification proceedings should be concluded to avoid indefinite delays in the main case. Introduce provisions for interim relief to prevent

unnecessary delays. To avoid the abuse of the system by using rectification claims as a tactic to delay proceedings, ensuring that genuine cases progress more swiftly.

SECTION 49. OFFENCES BY COMPANIES

Provision Overview:

Holds both companies and individuals responsible for GI-related offences. Directors or managers can avoid liability if they can show they were unaware of the offence or took steps to prevent it. This section ensures corporate accountability but provides safeguards for those who took reasonable steps to avoid involvement in offences.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- This section holds corporate officers liable for offences, but it lacks clarity on the degree of involvement or negligence required to establish personal liability. There's also no mechanism to identify the person most responsible when multiple officers are involved.
- It may be challenging to determine the exact responsibility of individual directors or managers, leading to potential evasion of liability by claiming ignorance of the offence.

Amendment Suggestion:

Clarify the degree of responsibility and involvement required for directors or managers to be held liable. There should be a tiered system of responsibility where penalties vary based on the individual's level of control or involvement in the infringement. This would prevent directors or managers from escaping liability by merely claiming ignorance while also ensuring that the true culprits face appropriate penalties.

SECTION 50. COGNIZANCE OF CERTAIN OFFENCES AND POLICE POWERS FOR SEARCH AND SEIZURE

Provision Overview:

This section empowers police officers to search and seize goods related to offences under the act. Courts take cognizance of specific offences only on written complaints by the Registrar. This gives enforcement authorities significant power to prevent the sale of counterfeit goods, ensuring timely intervention in GI infringement cases.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section gives police officers broad search and seizure powers but does not specify the process for obtaining the Registrar's opinion. Additionally, it lacks safeguards to prevent arbitrary or excessive use of these powers.
- The broad powers could lead to misuse by law enforcement without adequate checks, and delays in obtaining the Registrar's opinion may hinder the swift execution of raids or seizures.

Amendment Suggestion:

Establish a protocol for obtaining the Registrar's opinion in a timely manner before conducting searches and seizures. Include safeguards like a requirement for a written order from senior police officials or a judicial magistrate before acting on such powers. This helps to prevent misuse of search and seizure powers, ensuring that law enforcement actions are justified and proportionate.

SECTION 51. COSTS OF DEFENCE OF PROSECUTION

Provision Overview:

The court can order costs to be paid by either the complainant or the accused, depending on the outcome of the case. This provision ensures that frivolous lawsuits or malicious prosecutions can be penalised by imposing costs, thus deterring abuse of the legal system.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- This section allows the court to award costs to either party but does not provide a clear basis or formula for determining the amount. It leaves the decision entirely to judicial discretion, which could result in inconsistent awards.
- Lack of specific guidelines for awarding costs could lead to subjective decisions by the courts, creating uncertainty for litigants and potentially discouraging legitimate claims or defenses.

Amendment Suggestion:

Set clear criteria for determining the costs awarded by the court, such as taking into account the complexity of the case, the conduct of the parties, and whether the case is frivolous or legitimate. This would reduce arbitrary decisions on cost awards and provide clarity for both plaintiffs and defendants.

SECTION 52. LIMITATION OF PROSECUTION

Provision Overview:

Prosecution for offences must be initiated within three years from the commission of the offence or two years from its discovery, whichever is earlier. Establishes a clear timeframe for taking legal action, preventing indefinite threats of prosecution and ensuring prompt legal proceedings.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- While this section establishes time limits for prosecution, it does not specify how exceptions or delays caused by fraudulent concealment of offences might affect these limits.
- Offences related to GIs can sometimes take time to discover, especially in complex supply chains. Strict time limitations may prevent the prosecution of offences discovered after the limitation period has lapsed, even in cases of fraud.

Amendment Suggestion:

Include a provision that allows an extension of the prosecution period in cases where there is evidence of fraudulent concealment or deliberate evasion of detection by the offender. Protects against offenders who intentionally delay detection of their wrongful acts, ensuring that they can still be prosecuted even after the limitation period has passed.

SECTION 53. INFORMATION AS TO COMMISSION OF OFFENCE

Provision Overview:

Officers enforcing the act are protected from being compelled to disclose the source of information about an offence. Provides confidentiality to government officers involved in enforcement, encouraging whistleblowing and information sharing.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- This section protects officers from disclosing their sources of information, but it does not outline any mechanisms to verify the authenticity or reliability of the information they rely on.

- This could lead to potential misuse of authority if officers are not required to demonstrate that their actions are based on credible sources. It might also make it difficult for the accused to challenge actions based on undisclosed information.

Amendment Suggestion:

Introduce provisions requiring that any information received by officers be verified for credibility before action is taken. Additionally, establish a review mechanism where accused parties can challenge actions based on vague or unsupported claims. This would create checks to prevent arbitrary actions based on unreliable information and ensure fair treatment of accused parties.

SECTION 54. PUNISHMENT FOR ABETMENT IN INDIA OF ACTS DONE OUTSIDE INDIA

Provision Overview:

Individuals in India who abet offences related to GIs that occur outside the country can be prosecuted and punished as if the offence occurred within India. Expands the jurisdiction of Indian law to cover cross-border offences, ensuring that those involved in international counterfeiting of GIs can be held accountable.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- While it addresses abetment of offences occurring outside India, it is vague on how jurisdiction will be established, especially if the principal act takes place in a country with which India does not have legal agreements or treaties.
- Cross-border enforcement is inherently difficult, and this section does not provide practical guidelines for cooperation with foreign authorities, leading to potential difficulties in pursuing abettors involved in international offences.

Amendment Suggestion:

Develop a clear mechanism for establishing jurisdiction in cases where the principal act occurs outside India. Incorporate provisions for international cooperation with countries that have legal frameworks for protecting geographical indications. Cross-border enforcement of GI protection requires better-defined processes, ensuring smoother prosecution of abettors involved in international offences.

SECTION 55. PROTECTION OF ACTIONS TAKEN IN GOOD FAITH

Provision Overview:

Individuals acting in good faith under the provisions of the act are protected from legal actions. This safeguards government officials and others who perform their duties under the act from undue litigation, fostering proactive enforcement of the law.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The phrase “good faith” is not clearly defined, leaving scope for subjective interpretation. It does not specify whether negligent actions that are not malicious but still harmful could be protected under this section.
- The vague definition of “good faith” could lead to disputes over the legitimacy of actions taken by government officers, possibly resulting in frivolous legal challenges or shielding of negligent actions.

Amendment Suggestion:

Provide a definition of “good faith” and clarify the distinction between good faith actions and negligence. Include guidelines to help courts determine whether an action was genuinely in good faith or resulted from recklessness or negligence. This will prevent misuse of the “good faith” defense and ensure that negligent acts are not protected.

SECTION 56. CERTAIN PERSONS TO BE PUBLIC SERVANTS

Provision Overview:

Individuals appointed under the act are deemed public servants under the Indian Penal Code. Provides legal protection and establishes accountability for officials involved in the administration of the act.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The provision gives officers public servant status but does not elaborate on the specific protections or duties that come with this status under the act.
- The rights and responsibilities of such public servants need clearer delineation to avoid confusion, particularly when it comes to accountability for misuse of power or negligence.

Amendment Suggestion:

Elaborate on the duties and protections provided to public servants under this act. Specify the procedures for disciplinary action or accountability in cases where public servants misuse their powers. To provide clearer guidelines for the responsibilities of public servants and ensure they are held accountable for any misconduct.

SECTION 57. STAY OF PROCEEDINGS WHERE VALIDITY OF REGISTRATION IS QUESTIONED

Provision Overview:

Courts may stay infringement proceedings if the validity of the geographical indication is being challenged. The suit may resume once the question of validity is resolved. This section prevents unnecessary litigation while the validity of a GI is under question, ensuring that courts focus on legitimate cases.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section does not define a clear time limit for the stay of proceedings, nor does it provide measures to prevent abuse of this provision through frivolous challenges to the validity of the registration.
- The stay of proceedings could be used as a delaying tactic, slowing down infringement lawsuits and denying timely justice to legitimate GI holders.

Amendment Suggestion:

Limit the stay period for rectification proceedings to a maximum time frame, such as six months, unless there are exceptional circumstances. Also, require the party challenging the registration to provide substantial evidence of the GI's invalidity before the stay is granted. To prevent frivolous claims from causing unnecessary delays and ensure that only legitimate challenges to GI registrations lead to a stay of proceedings.

SECTION 58. APPLICATION FOR RECTIFICATION OF REGISTER TO BE MADE TO HIGH COURT

Provision Overview

In cases where the validity of a GI is challenged in an infringement suit, the application for rectification must be made to the High Court. Ensures that only the High Court can deal with

complex matters related to the rectification of GIs, maintaining a higher standard of judicial review.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The act mandates that rectification proceedings related to GIs must go directly to the High Court. However, this could burden the High Courts, and there are no provisions for streamlining such cases or dealing with them expediently.
- High Courts, already overburdened, may face delays in handling GI-related rectification applications, causing further delays in resolving infringement disputes.

Amendment Suggestion:

Consider establishing special benches or designated judges in the High Courts to handle GI-related rectification cases, or alternatively, allow lower courts to handle less complex rectification matters. To reduce the burden on High Courts, speeds up the rectification process and allows for faster resolution of disputes.

SECTION 59. IMPLIED WARRANTY ON SALE OF INDICATED GOODS

Provision Overview:

When a geographical indication is applied to goods, the seller implicitly warrants its genuineness unless stated otherwise in writing. This provision protects consumers from counterfeit goods, ensuring that sellers are held accountable for the authenticity of GIs.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- The section presumes that sellers always have knowledge of the authenticity of the geographical indication, but it fails to address situations where sellers may have unknowingly dealt in counterfeit goods.
- Small retailers or intermediaries may face liability even if they had no means to verify the authenticity of the GI. This could lead to unfair penalization of innocent parties in the supply chain.

Amendment Suggestion:

Add provisions requiring due diligence by sellers, such as obtaining certificates of authenticity for GIs. In cases where sellers unknowingly deal in counterfeit goods, provide a defence if they can show they took reasonable steps to verify the authenticity. Ensure that

sellers are accountable but also protects those who may unknowingly sell counterfeit goods by encouraging them to verify their sources.

SECTION 60. POWERS OF REGISTRAR

Provision Overview:

The Registrar is granted powers akin to those of a civil court, such as receiving evidence, summoning witnesses, and reviewing decisions. This equips the Registrar with judicial-like powers to ensure the effective enforcement of the act, providing a robust administrative mechanism for GI protection.

Legal Lacunas Identified:

- While the Registrar has been given extensive powers, the act does not specify clear mechanisms for reviewing or appealing decisions made by the Registrar. The section is also vague on how costs will be determined.
- Broad powers vested in the Registrar without adequate oversight mechanisms could lead to potential misuse. Additionally, decisions on cost awards may be inconsistent without clearer guidelines.

Amendment Suggestion:

Provide clear procedures for appealing decisions made by the Registrar. Introduce guidelines for determining costs in disputes and allow for a neutral review of the Registrar's decisions by an independent body or tribunal. To ensure transparency and fairness in the exercise of the Registrar's powers, preventing arbitrary decisions and allowing parties to seek redress if needed.